

MIR from scratch: the building of an Automatic Emotion Recognition task

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Abstract

A step by step guidance through the fundamentals of an Automatic Emotion Recognition (AER) task is offered in the present dissertation. This includes all the phases that usually characterise the process: feature engineering, feature selection, model engineering and model selection. An in-depth presentation of the four of them (theoretical background, chronological procedures and basic examples) is provided along with some typical experiments in the field carried out at the end of the project. All features (Low Level Descriptors and Statistical Functionals), machine learning models (Multi-Layer Perceptron neural network and RNN-LSTM) and complementary functions and scripts have been carefully coded by the author in MATLAB environment, giving birth to a pair of new toolboxes for Music Information Retrieval (MIR) among other fields: the Acoustic Feature Extraction Set and the Machine Learning toolbox. The results of the experiments generally point towards good predictions, and some relevant applications and betterments might be extracted from this piece of work.

Declaration

I do hereby declare that this dissertation was composed by myself and that the work described within is my own, except where explicitly stated otherwise.

Alejandro Delgado Luezas
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Chapter 1

Introduction

Since its establishment as a discipline where machine learning and Digital Signal Processing (DSP) meet, Music Information Retrieval's (MIR) growing popularity has surely amazed more than one researcher during the last decades. But, should it? After all, music has always played a very important role in our lives as human beings. The sole idea that a piece of code could recommend you a song that you would probably like is exciting, and nowadays these engines are also capable of performing automatic genre, instrument and chord recognition among others.

Some of the tasks referenced in the last paragraph have definitely grown better over time, allowing both musicians and music lovers to refine their compasses when it comes to enjoying the art form. Now, some promising subfields in MIR are emerging to contribute to this goal, and this is certainly the case of Automatic Emotion Recognition (AER). This one started to be studied seriously fifteen years ago, what makes it a fairly young sub-discipline in MIR. And although its most representative application to everyday life consists in recommending music based on the actual mood of the listener, emotion can also be taken as a weighted parameter so to recommend music as a general practice, as a certain listener may be very drawn to listen to sad music, for instance.

In order to recognise emotion, one can use either the multidimensional model in psychology or the categorical one. The former is based on the valence of a certain stimulus (how positive or negative it is) and its arousal (how stimulating or relaxing it is), and the latter deals directly with discrete and sometimes mutually exclusive categories such as happiness, anger, sadness, etc. Though some significant correlation has been found between these two models, they are analysed separately in AER, as machine learning algorithms generally perform classification (categorical) and regression (multidimensional) tasks.

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this project is to shed light on what is underneath a typical MIR process. Namely, to carry out an in-depth study of the logical foundations of the algorithms used for such end to later implement them. The author has coded a set of Low Level Descriptors and statistical descriptors for audio file analysis, along with a multilayer perceptron (neural network) for machine learning processes in order to achieve Automatic Emotion Recognition given several databases. The building of these tools has been done from scratch, discarding any available toolbox with pre-built functions in the process, and thus allowing the author to dive deeper into both DSP and deep learning.

In chapter 2, the theoretical foundations of the main processes are explained in detail as a methodological guidance throughout the text. In chapter 3, results of the experiment are discussed and analysed and, finally, conclusions are drawn from the overall project in chapter 4. There are also two appendices available where some relevant code, pseudocode and further clarifications about the structure of the digital archive submitted with this dissertation are gathered.

Chapter 2

Methodology

In the present chapter, the author will discuss the central topics that play an important role when introducing the results of a certain experiment in MIR and AER, helping to shed light on its dynamics. The chapter is organised as if it were the map of the project, providing an extensive overview of its main phases to allow the reader to fully engage in the Music Information Retrieval process. The whole process of getting emotional information from raw audio files is outlined in the following manner:

1. **Feature Engineering:** Coding and extraction of Low Level Descriptors (LLD) and audio features.
2. **Feature Selection:** Selection of the most relevant audio features.
3. **Model Engineering:** Coding of the machine learning maps of audio features to emotions (in our case, Artificial Neural Networks).
4. **Model Selection:** Selection of the optimal hyper-parameters of each Neural Network in order to achieve the best performance possible.

2.1 Preamble: Datasets and the Emotional Models

Before diving into the nature of the features' algorithms, a brief overview of both the emotional models in the field of psychology and the used datasets throughout the project is presented below.

The Emotional Models

When identifying emotion, there are two main paths that psychologists have embraced over the years: the *categorical* and the *dimensional* model [2].

Figure 2.1: This figure introduces the two emotional models in a simple plane. As there's a significant correlation between these methods, one can represent discrete classes of emotion as points in this space and, therefore, as a function of the main dimensions: arousal (energy, activation) and valence (positivity, benefit).

The **categorical model** is the one that we as humans are most familiarised to, as it's the one we use in day to day language to describe how we feel. We may say we're angry, happy, serene, bored, sad, upset... etc. However, unlike the way we're going to use this model, we also assign some implicit continuum to these categories (like happy-sad, calm-nervous or even more complex like ecstasy-happiness-joy-boredom-sadness-depression) that gives the appearance of one-dimensionality to the model while treating its categories as if they were somewhere along that line or even as dimensional extremes. In that fashion, one might say something like 'I feel more motivated than I felt yesterday' or 'I'm quite sad, but not as sad as when I was fired'. In our case, though, we'll use these categories in a closed binary context, meaning that one may feel happy or not, reducing the line to a very specific region due to the complexity of emotions. This will ultimately make the emotional annotations (classification) unevenly distributed, as the judgements will fall in the 'not happy' class the vast majority of times (note that 'not happy' doesn't necessarily equal 'sad', but the fact that the subject wouldn't describe the song with the 'happy' tag in an everyday basis).

The **dimensional model**, on the other hand, attempts to describe these categories above by using multi-dimensional scaling. Several experiments have been carried out in order to assert the optimal number of dimensions to display the categories spatially and, as some investigations point towards tension as an also relevant dimension, the most

accepted model is composed of two dimensions: *arousal* and *valence*. The former would be a perfect analogous to the subjective intensity of the feeling, meaning that the more active or alert a stimulus makes one person feel, the higher the score this person should annotate in the arousal dimension. The latter, in an independent yet complementary way, is used to describe the subjective experience of positivity embedded in the arising feeling, meaning that the more fulfilling a stimulus makes one person feel, the higher the score this person should annotate in this valence dimension. In consequence, we have a two dimensional plane where we can, with a relevant degree of confidence, place the categories in the last paragraph (like sadness or nervousness).

This dimensional model of emotions has been accepted very well in the scientific community, and more and more studies are being published supporting the fact that all possible extra emotional dimensions can (and should) be reduced to arousal and valence uniquely, even in music [4]. In fact, it happens to be the most used emotional model in AER, as it's far more simple and straightforward than the categorical model, and even appear to be more accurate when working with emotions in MIR [5]. Also, unlike in our method, studies involving High Level Descriptors (tonality, rhythm, tempo... etc) have been proved successful when identifying emotions both dimensionally and categorically [6], approach that sometimes complements the Low Level Descriptors' one well.

In this particular project, we will arrange experiments that involve both of these emotional models and study their manageability and handiness in order to retrieve an optimal description of emotions.

2.1.1 Soundtrack Database

- Dataset Type: Music (film soundtracks).
- Individual Participant Annotations: No (Mean).
- Data Scale: From 1 (minimum) to 8 (maximum) in both valence and arousal.
- Annotation Type: Static.
- Number of audio files: 460 (360 from the first set plus 110 from the second set).
- Duration of audio files: Variable (15-30 seconds approx.).
- Sampling Rate of audio files: 44100 Hz.
- Format of audio files: MPEG layer 3 (MP3).

2.1.2 Emotify Database

- Dataset Type: Music (modern songs and classical pieces).
- Individual Participant Anotations: Yes.
- Data Scale: Binary (No valence nor arousal).
- Annotation Type: Static.
- Number of audio files: 400.
- Duration of audio files: 1 minute.
- Sampling Rate of audio files: 44100 Hz.
- Format of audio files: MPEG layer 3 (MP3).

2.1.3 Emotion in Music Database (1000 songs)

- Dataset Type: Music (modern songs and classical pieces).
- Individual Participant Anotations: No (Mean + Std)
- Data Scale: From 1 (minimum) to 9 (maximum) in both valence and arousal.
- Annotation Type: Dynamic (mean values as final static data).
- Number of audio files: 744 (once duplicates were removed)
- Duration of audio files: 45 seconds (first 15 seconds non annotated dynamically).
- Sampling Rate of audio files: 44100 Hz.
- Format of audio files: MPEG layer 3 (MP3).

2.2 Feature Engineering

The first part of the process consists in the coding and extraction of the relevant features (physical characteristics) of the audio files to be analysed. We used Matlab 2016R for such purpose. The process of obtaining the feature matrix of an audio database can also be reduced to the following steps:

Figure 2.2: This figure schematises the dynamics of a feature extraction process from a given audio database. Both the LLD matrix and the Feature matrix are retrieved.

1. Take one audio file and **divide** it into frames of approximately 25 ms (1024 samples at 44.1k sample rate). This division is done because it is believed that the spectrum of each of these frames is approximately constant [3] (like if it were a photograph of the audio file in that moment), and we can capture the events happening in the file more accurately in time.
2. Compute and extract the relevant **Low Level Descriptors (LLD)** like loudness, energy, spectral entropy, MFCC... from each frame and store the data in a matrix of size $[N^o \text{ frames} \times N^o \text{ LLD}]$. In our case, there will be 40 raw LLD vectors plus their deltas (derivatives through time), making a total of 80 LLD.
3. Apply **Statistical Descriptors** like mean, standard deviation, quartiles, percentiles... to each LLD vector in the matrix to retrieve real numbers (features). This allows us to capture the temporal dynamics of the LLD without directly working with all the data extracted from the frames. It gives us the **Feature Vector**, which has a total length of 3081 in our case.
4. Repeat all the steps above for each audio file in the database to get the final **Feature Matrix** (2 dimensional one of size $[N^o \text{ files} \times N^o \text{ features}]$) and **LLD Matrix** (3 dimensional one of size $[N^o \text{ files} \times N^o \text{ frames} \times N^o \text{ LLD}]$) for static and dynamic models respectively.

For the present project, we've coded most of the Low Level Descriptors and Statistical Functionals that appear in the *ComParE acoustic feature dataset* from scratch. This list of functions has been used extensively in MIR for LLD-based feature

	Group
4 ENERGY RELATED LLD	
Sum of auditory spectrum (loudness)	Prosodic
Sum of RASTA-style filtered auditory spectrum	Prosodic
RMS energy, zero-crossing rate	Prosodic
55 SPECTRAL LLD	
RASTA-style auditory spectrum, bands 1–26 (0–8 kHz)	Spectral
MFCC 1–14	Cepstral
Spectral energy 250–650 Hz, 1 k–4 kHz	Spectral
Spectral roll off point 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 0.90	Spectral
Spectral flux, centroid, entropy, slope	Spectral
Psychoacoustic sharpness, harmonicity	Spectral
Spectral variance, skewness, kurtosis	Spectral
6 VOICING RELATED LLD	
F_0 (SHS and viterbi smoothing)	Prosodic
Prob. of voice	Sound quality
Log. HNR, Jitter (local, delta), Shimmer (local)	Sound quality

Figure 2.3: The ComParE acoustic feature set: Low Level Descriptors. The RASTA-style filtered auditory spectrum, both the sum and the bands, and the probability of voice weren't finally coded because of the lack of existing literature at hand.

extraction. Figures 2.3 and 2.4 display the list in its entirety, and we'll explain them in detail in the next subsections.

2.2.1 Low Level Descriptors

In this subsection, the author provides a brief overview of each of the main Low Level Descriptors used to extract sonic characteristics from the audio frames. Just for clarity purposes, here's some basic notation used throughout the listing:

- x : Time-domain signal of the frame.
- $|X|$: Magnitude of the frequency-domain signal of the frame (Fourier Transform of the time-domain signal).
- N : Length of the frame in samples.

Loudness (1 LLD)

We could very informally define loudness as a psychoacoustical version of sound energy. It's subjective by definition and, in order to retrieve its value, it's recommended to pre-filter the signal with an A, B or C weighting filter. It also happens to depend on the

	Group
FUNCTIONALS APPLIED TO LLD/Δ LLD	
Quartiles 1–3, 3 inter-quartile ranges	Percentiles
1% Percentile (\approx min), 99% percentile (\approx max)	Percentiles
Percentile range 1–99%	Percentiles
Position of min/max, range (max – min)	Temporal
Arithmetic mean ¹ , root quadratic mean	Moments
Contour centroid, flatness	Temporal
Standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis	Moments
Rel. duration LLD is above 25/50/75/90% range	Temporal
Rel. duration LLD is rising	Temporal
Rel. duration LLD has positive curvature	Temporal
Gain of linear prediction (LP), LP coefficients 1–5	Modulation
Mean, max, min, SD of segment length ²	Temporal
FUNCTIONALS APPLIED TO LLD ONLY	
Mean value of peaks	Peaks
Mean value of peaks – arithmetic mean	Peaks
Mean/SD of inter peak distances	Peaks
Amplitude mean of peaks, of minima	Peaks
Amplitude range of peaks	Peaks
Mean/SD of rising/falling slopes	Peaks
Linear regression slope, offset, quadratic error	Regression
Quadratic regression a, b, offset, quadratic error	Regression
Percentage of non-zero frames ³	Temporal

¹Arithmetic mean of LLD/positive Δ LLD. ²Not applied to voice related LLD except F_0 . ³Only applied to F_0 .

Figure 2.4: The ComParE acoustic feature set: Statistical Functionals. The gain of LPCs wasn't finally coded because of the lack of existing literature at hand.

intensity of the signal by the Stevens' power law [7]:

$$Loudness = kI^{0.3} \quad (2.1)$$

where k is the calibration constant and I is the intensity of the sound, proportional to the square of the energy, given right below.

Energy (3 LLD)

Energy, as defined in Digital Signal Processing, does not equal its homonym physical concept, though its behaviour and role in the field is somewhat analogous to this last one. It's simply defined as follows [8]:

$$Energy = \sum_n |X|(n)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

Zero Crossing Rate (1 LLD)

This is defined as how often a signal’s amplitude changes its sign during its lifetime. One can calculate it by counting the times that the signal changes sign and then dividing this number by the length of the signal in samples, as described by the following equation [8].

$$ZCR = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} 1_{\mathbb{R}<0}(x(n) \cdot x(n-1)) \quad (2.3)$$

This is a quick way to estimate the noisiness of the frame.

Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) (18 LLD)

The MFCCs [9] have been of vital importance in speech processing and have some relevance when analysing music and audio in general. They help to represent a certain signal spectrum as one based on human auditory perception by applying a filterbank (an array of band-pass filters) to the signal and analysing these separately through these coefficients.

They help shedding light to what’s relevant in the audio spectrum to a certain task and discard what’s not useful like ambient noise. In speech processing it’s a common practice to downsample the signal and even taking a shorter Discrete Fourier Transform (no need for more bins), as they get the relevant information they were searching in speech. In music analysis, though, there’s no common agreement when selecting these hyper-parameters. For that reason, the author of the present project decided to expand the range of some of these parameters in case one ends up missing some relevant information for emotion retrieving.

The process involved in getting the MFCCs [10] starts from selecting the lower and upper analysis frequencies. In our case, we’ll choose 100 and 11000 Hz. Then, we’ll convert these two frequencies from Hz to Mels (a psychoacoustical scale based on the Fletcher-Munson curves) by applying the following formula:

$$M(f) = 1125 \log\left(1 + \frac{f}{700}\right) \quad (2.4)$$

After that, we’ll decide the number of band-pass filters in the filterbank, 34 in our case, and interpolate between the lower and upper analysis frequencies, getting a total of 36 equally spaced Mel frequencies. Then, we’ll convert these 36 frequencies back to

Hz by arranging the last equation in the following way:

$$M^{-1}(m) = 700e^{\frac{m}{1125}-1} \quad (2.5)$$

Now that we have our frequency points between 100 and 11000 Hz, we can proceed to build the filterbank. In order to do that, we'll use the conditional expression below:

$$H_m(k) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } k < f(m-1) \\ \frac{k - f(m-1)}{f(m) - f(m-1)}, & \text{if } f(m-1) \leq k \leq f(m) \\ \frac{f(m+1) - k}{f(m+1) - f(m)}, & \text{if } f(m) \leq k \leq f(m+1) \\ 0, & \text{if } k > f(m+1) \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

where M would be the number of filters in the filterbank and f stands for indexed frequency.

Subsequently, we can apply this filterbank to the periodogram-based power spectral estimate of the frame, defined as follows:

$$P(n) = \frac{E(n)}{N} \quad (2.7)$$

where E is the energy. And, finally, we take the logarithm and then the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) of all these 34 energies derived from this last application of the filterbank. The first 18 numbers derived from this process (related to the first 18 filters in the filterbank) are our MFCCs.

Spectral Roll-Off Frequency (4 LLD)

The roll-off frequency is simply the frequency under which a certain percentage of the total spectral energy falls upon. We will retrieve four roll-off points: 25%, 50%, 75% and 90%.

Spectral Flux (1 LLD)

The spectral flux is commonly defined as the total distance in magnitude between the spectrum of the current frame and the one of the previous frame. It's formally defined as follows [11]:

$$Flux = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \frac{(|X_{old}(n)| - |X_{new}(n)|) + \left| |X_{old}(n)| - |X_{new}(n)| \right|}{2} \quad (2.8)$$

Spectral Centroid, Variance, Skewness and Kurtosis (4 LLD)

These four descriptors are born from the treating of the frequency spectrum of the audio frame as a statistical distribution whose values are the frequencies and whose probabilities are equivalent to the normalised amplitudes. In that fashion, one can apply some of the most fundamental descriptors in the field: the centroid, the variance, the skewness and the kurtosis [12].

The *spectral centroid* (frequency) is often informally defined as the barycenter or the center of mass of the spectrum.

$$Centroid = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(n)|X|(n)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |X|(n)} \quad (2.9)$$

The *spectral variance*, on the other hand, is defined as the spread of the spectrum around its mean value.

$$Variance = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (f(n) - Centroid)^2 |X|(n)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |X|(n)} \quad (2.10)$$

The *spectral skewness* can be thought as a measure of the asymmetry of the spectrum around its mean value.

$$Skewness = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (f(n) - Centroid)^3 |X|(n)}{Variance^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |X|(n)} \quad (2.11)$$

And finally, the *spectral kurtosis* gives us a measure of the flatness of the spectrum around its mean value.

$$Kurtosis = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (f(n) - Centroid)^4 |X|(n)}{Variance^2 \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |X|(n)} \quad (2.12)$$

Spectral Entropy (1 LLD)

The entropy descriptor allows us to measure the peakiness of a given spectrum if we convert it to a probability mass function (PMF), and it's widely used in speech processing [13].

As the spectrum is not already a PMF, the first step in this relatively simple process

is to do this conversion in the following manner:

$$PMF(n) = \frac{|X|(n)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |X|(n)} \quad (2.13)$$

Then, as the definitive step, we can calculate the spectral entropy from the PMF that we've gathered. In this sense:

$$Entropy = - \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} PMF(n) \cdot \log_2(PMF(n)) \quad (2.14)$$

Spectral Slope (1 LLD)

The spectral slope comes from applying a linear regression to the spectrum and getting the slope coefficient. In this fashion, the linear regression equation for the spectrum could be written as:

$$f(|X|) = a \cdot |X| + b \quad (2.15)$$

where a is the *slope* of the spectrum.

Sharpness (1 LLD)

Sharpness is a psychoacoustical parameter that essentially measures the high frequency content of a certain sound. The greater the number of higher frequencies in relation to the lower ones, the sharper the sound will be.

In order to get it [14], we firstly calculate the loudness spectrum (built with the loudness of each frequency bin) and, after having converted the frequency vector in Hz to Barks (a psychoacoustical scale), we can place each frequency magnitude in the loudness spectrum to its equivalent place in the Bark scale, usually from 0 to 24. We used the traunmuller conversion from frequency in Hz to Barks in order to do this mapping.

Once all that is done, we can proceed to the sharpness calculation by also building the function $g'(z)$, which is constant for lower frequencies (not the target) and a polynomial function of the Bark continuum for higher ones (target frequencies). The integration of this function across the whole Bark scale is what gives us the final sharpness value:

$$S = c \cdot \frac{\int_0^{24} N' \cdot g'(z) \cdot z \cdot dz}{N} \quad (2.16)$$

where

$$g'(z) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z < 14 \\ 0.00012 \cdot z^4 - 0.0056 \cdot z^3 + 0.1 \cdot z^2 - 0.81 \cdot z + 3.51, & \text{if } z \geq 14 \end{cases} \quad (2.17)$$

Fundamental Frequency (1 LLD)

In order to calculate the fundamental frequency (f_0) of the frame (this is generally its lowest most audible frequency), the author of the present project has followed the YIN method [15]. This approach consists in firstly calculating the *difference function* for a certain window semi-length W (generally of a third of the total length of the frame) and time invariant τ for pivoting when moving across the values of the frame:

$$d_t(\tau) = \sum_{j=1}^W (x_j - x_{j+\tau})^2 \quad (2.18)$$

Then, we take the *cumulative mean normalised function* out of this difference equation, which happens to improve the algorithm.

$$d'_t(\tau) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \tau = 0 \\ \frac{d_t(\tau)}{\frac{1}{\tau} \sum_{j=1}^{\tau} d_t(j)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.19)$$

Lastly, we find the minimum of this last function by doing parabolic interpolation to improve resolution and finally state that the fundamental frequency is:

$$f_0 = \frac{Fs}{lcm\min(d'_t(\tau))} \quad (2.20)$$

where the *lcm\min* function aludes to the location (index) of the minimum.

Inharmonicity (1 LLD)

The inharmonicity of a spectrum is a measure of the distance from the peaks of a spectrum to the place where the harmonic partials (multiples of the fundamental frequency) should lie. The greater the distance, the higher the inharmonicity. It is computed as an energy weighted distance [12]:

$$IH = \frac{2}{f_0} \cdot \frac{\sum_h |f(h) - h \cdot f_0| \cdot E^2(h)}{\sum_h E^2(h)} \quad (2.21)$$

where E is the energy and h is an integer vector that goes from 1 to the number of harmonics one would want to evaluate.

Harmonic to Noise Ratio (1 LLD)

The Harmonic to Noise Ratio, as its denomination suggests, is the ratio between the amount of harmonicity in the signal and its amount of noisiness [16]. We can get to its formal expression from the premise that a signal $s(t)$ is composed by both a harmonic $h(t)$ and a noisy $n(t)$ content

$$s(t) = h(t) + n(t) \quad (2.22)$$

Once agreed on that, we can make the following approximations for the autocorrelation expression, where T_0 is the fundamental period of the signal (the inverse of the fundamental frequency f_0):

$$R_{xx}(T_0) = \frac{1}{N - T_0} \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} s(t)s(t - T_0) = \frac{1}{N - T_0} \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} (h(t) + n(t))(h(t - T_0) + n(t - T_0)) \quad (2.23)$$

Expanding this expression we get:

$$R_{xx}(T_0) = \frac{1}{N - T_0} \left(\sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} h(t)h(t - T_0) + \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} h(t)n(t - T_0) + \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} h(t - T_0)n(t) + \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} n(t)n(t - T_0) \right) \quad (2.24)$$

Now, by saying that the harmonic part of the signal $h(t)$ and the noisy part of the signal $n(t)$ aren't correlated at all in this harmonic context (with T_0) and that $n(t)$ isn't also self-correlated in this fashion, we can neglect the impact of the last three terms in the summation, remaining the first one:

$$R_{xx}(T_0) \approx \frac{1}{N - T_0} \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} h(t)h(t - T_0) \quad (2.25)$$

Also, we can still make a final approximation by saying that $h(t - T_0) \approx h(t)$, and therefore:

$$R_{xx}(T_0) \approx \frac{1}{N - T_0} \sum_{t=T_0}^{N-1} h(t)h(t) \quad (2.26)$$

With that in mind, the Harmonic to Noise Ratio would then be the following:

$$HNR = \frac{R_{xx}(T_0)}{R_{xx}(0) - R_{xx}(T_0)} \quad (2.27)$$

Jitter (1 LLD)

Jitter is defined as the average absolute difference between consecutive periods divided by the average period. The expression for this descriptor has the following form [17]:

$$Jitter = \frac{N}{N-1} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |T_i - T_{i+1}|}{\sum_{i=1}^N T_i} \quad (2.28)$$

Shimmer (1 LLD)

Shimmer is defined as the average absolute difference between the amplitudes of consecutive periods divided by the average amplitude. The expression for this descriptor has the following form [17]:

$$Shimmer = \frac{N}{N-1} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |A_i - A_{i+1}|}{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i} \quad (2.29)$$

2.2.2 Statistical Functionals

- **Quartiles and IQRs:** When the LLD vectors are sorted in ascending order, the first quartile would be the magnitude in the sorted vector that separates the lowest 25% of the data from the highest 75%; the second quartile would be the magnitude that separates the vector's values in half (median); and the third quartile would be the magnitude that separates the lowest 75% of the data from the highest 25%. The first IQR would be the difference of the value of the first quartile and the first term of the sorted vector; the second IQR would be the difference of the value of the third quartile and the value of the first quartile; and the third IQR would be the difference of the last term of the sorted vector with the value of the third quartile. (6 SF per LLD)
- **Percentiles and IPR:** Both 1st and 99th percentiles are calculated (the values below which 1% and 99% of the data can be found respectively), along with the Inter-Percentile Range; that is the difference between the 99th percentile with the 1st percentile. (3 SF per LLD)
- **Location of minimum and maximum:** Indices in the LLD vectors where its minimum or maximum takes place. (2 SF per LLD)

- **Range:** Difference between the minimum and maximum magnitude in an LLD vector. (1 SF per LLD)
- **Mean and RMS:** Arithmetic mean and Root Mean Square of an LLD vector. (2 SF per LLD)
- **Centroid, Skewness and Kurtosis:** As defined in 2.2.1 but with the indexing vector (from 0 to N-1) instead of the frequency vector (spectral). (3 SF per LLD)
- **Flatness:** This is defined as the geometric mean of the LLD vector divided by its arithmetic mean [12]. (1 SF per LLD)
- **Standard Deviation** (1 SF per LLD)
- **Relative Durations:** Normalised durations of when the LLD is above 25%, 50%, 75% and 90% of the data values, when the LLD is rising ($LLD' > 0$) and when the LLD has positive curvature ($LLD'' > 0$) (6 SF per LLD)
- **Linear Prediction Coefficients (LPC):** Very relevant statistical tool in speech processing and synthesis, this descriptor, it can also be used to study the dynamics of a certain musical piece, though with notable limitations. It's based on the idea that voice (and audio, in our case) can be modeled as a linear combination of a certain number of samples p plus an error signal [18]. In our case, we've taken five ($p = 5$) LPCs for our analysis and therefore 5 number of samples. (5 SF per LLD)
- **Mean and RMS of Peaks** (2 SF per LLD)
- **Mean and Standard Deviation of Inter-Peak Distances** (2 SF per LLD)
- **Mean of minima** (1 SF per LLD)
- **Range of Peaks:** Difference between the lowest minimum and the highest peak in an LLD vector. (2 SF per LLD)
- **Mean and Standard Deviation of Rising and Falling slopes** (4 SF per LLD)
- **Linear Regression Parameters:** slope, offset and quadratic error of a linear regression applied to the LLD vectors. (3 SF per LLD)
- **Quadratic Regression Parameters:** curvature, slope, offset and quadratic error of a quadratic regression applied to the LLD vectors. (4 SF per LLD)
- **Percentage of non-zero terms (for Fundamental Frequency only)** (1 SF)

2.3 Feature Selection

If we feed 3081-length input vectors to a neural network, it would surely take a really long time to learn, apart from achieving a mediocre result given the large dimensionality that it implies. Therefore, it's generally a good idea to select the most relevant input features for a certain set of outputs to proceed with the mapping.

When selecting features, one may take one of two paths: *model dependent* or *model independent* approaches. The former is *a posteriori*, meaning that it evaluates how well potential feature sets perform on the task at hand; in other words, it takes different combinations of features, feeds them to the neural network, record the result for each performance and retrieve the feature set that achieves the best result. The latter, on the other hand, is *a priori*, meaning that doesn't care about the nature of the machine learning algorithm and just studies the feature matrix properties along with the target matrix containing the emotional content of the analysed audio files. As there are far too many features, their combination would result in an exhaustive search that would surely consume a lot of time. Thus, the preferred method for this task is the *model independent* one.

In this fashion we're going to use a simple version of the recently popularised **Correlation-based Feature Selection (CFS)** [19]. This model essentially ranks the features according to their betterness and outputs a given percentage of them starting from the best positioned ones. This 'betterness' of the features is simply calculated by taking the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of each feature vector (of length equal to the number of audio files) with the rest of them and taking the mean of each contribution (given by $Corr(X, Y)$) and also the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of each feature vector with the target matrix (of length equal to the N^o emotional dimensions to be mapped) and also taking the mean of each contribution (given by $Corr(X, T)$). Once we got these numbers, we can calculate the rank of the feature X with the following expression:

$$Rank(X) = \frac{Corr(X, T)}{Corr(X, Y)} \quad (2.30)$$

where X is the current evaluated feature, Y is the rest of the features in the input feature matrix and T is the target/output matrix. Hence, the features that happen to be the most correlated with the target matrix (it provides aiming to the final feature set) and, at the same time, the least correlated with the rest of the features (it eliminates redundancies in the final feature set) will rank best and, therefore, be the preferential features to use.

2.4 Model Engineering

Now that we have our final Feature matrix and LLD matrix, we can start thinking about the machine learning algorithms that we have to use in order to map these audio characteristics to actual emotions, either from the dimensional model or the categorical one. The author of the present project has considered many possible approaches to these tasks and, in the end, decided to use **Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)** [20] [21] as the appropriate algorithm to use. These are computer algorithms that are based on (or even mimic) human's brain dynamics when relating some type of data into another type.

Among the reasons involved in this decision, one can find that neural networks' logic is one of the most flexible both for classification and regression tasks. Apart from achieving good results in a reasonable amount of time for static annotations, it has also been developed sequential models that can process dynamic annotations as well. Hence, and taking into account the static and dynamic nature of our databases' annotations, the idea of diving completely in the world of neural networks and ending up having a solid understanding of how they work and how to apply them was attractive enough to pursue it.

Two neural networks have been coded for this project: the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) and the Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN-LSTM). The former is capable of achieving both regression of static annotations (for the Soundtrack Database, given in 2.1.1), and classification for static annotations (for the Emotify Database, given in 2.1.2), while the latter can model dynamic annotations in a regression framework (for the Emotion in Music Database, given in 2.1.3).

2.4.1 The Multi-Layer Perceptron

The original perceptron algorithm was invented in 1957 and, although it took some time for researchers and machine learning operators to really value its potential in the field, it has been in a constant period of improvement since its birth. The Multi-Layer Perceptron algorithm, in particular, is the most known and basic algorithm that's built as an actual Artificial Neural Network.

At the moment, some more advanced models of neural networks are used instead of the Multi-Layer Perceptron on a regular basis when challenging tasks are the order of the day, but when in doubt one can always come back and revisit this fairly intuitive and relatively simple model to learn from the input data and make the required predictions.

Figure 2.5: Scheme showing the basic architecture of a multi-layer perceptron. Each little coloured spheres represent the neurons or units and each line connecting the neurons represents a weight parameter.

MLP Architecture

The Multi-Layer Perceptron is composed of the following characteristic parts:

- Input Layer: This is the first layer of the MLP, which stores the inputs for the mapping process, each in one neuron or unit. Here is where we'll feed the extracted features for each audio file.
- Output Layer: This is the last layer of the MLP, which stores the outputs for the mapping process, each in one neuron or unit. Here is where we'll plug the emotional data for each audio file.
- Hidden Layers: These are the intermediate layers of the MLP, between the input and the output layers and, though there are optimal quantities of neurons depending on the system to be performed the mapping on, they can have as many neurons as the user wants. These ones store all the intermediate calculations taking place in the process of getting the emotional information out of audio features. The more hidden layers the MLP has, the more complex the model will be; which is not necessarily good, as a complex model for a fairly simple mapping could be an obvious cause for the neural network to 'misbehave' and ultimately perform poorly.
- Weight Matrices: These will be the 'synapses' of the neural network. Our map. They connect all the neurons in the layers sequentially by matrix multiplication (from the input layer to the output layer passing through the hidden layers) and are the ones to be updated in each iteration of the MLP, thus making them the

essential instrument to get after a learning process. Their duty is to multiply the received values and send them to the neuron in the next layer to be added to the rest of its connections.

- Biases: These are constants to be added to each of the connections between layers, and determine the degree of displacement of the numerical value entering in each of the layers. They're specially useful for preparing this value to the imminent application of the activation function (see below in 'Fundamental Parameters'), as one must make sure that it falls into the effective region of this function.
- Hyper-Parameters: These are the parameters that directly influence the performance of a neural network dictating its dynamics, in particular the harshness or softness of some particular processes and the complexity of the model. They can be optimised (i.e. to find the combination of these parameters' magnitudes that brings the best performance out of the neural network).
 - *Number of Selected Features*
 - *Number of Hidden Layers*
 - *Number of Neurons in each Hidden Layer*
 - *Number of Epochs*
 - *Learning Rate*
 - *Momentum*
 - *Regularization Parameter*

We'll explain the last four hyper-parameters later on.

- Fundamental Parameters: These parameters, unlike the hyper-parameters, cannot be or are not recommended to be optimised, as they are categorical and also build the most solid foundation of the neural network's dynamics.
 - *Activation Functions*: These are both linear and non-linear functions that are applied to the value entering in a neuron before it goes out to reach the next layer. There are several activation functions to be considered depending on the task at hand, though the most popular ones have a sigmoid form, which convert the real numbers acquired into probabilities between 0 and 1, making hidden layer dynamics more manageable and even effective.
 - *Cost Function*: This is the metric for the loss when evaluating the learning process.
 - *Performance Metric*: This is the metric for the error when evaluating the testing process.

- *Scaling Functions*: They are applied to the input and output matrices in order to better organise the data they store, aiming for a betterment in the overall performance of the neural network. Typical examples of scaling are normalization (for outputs) and standardization (for inputs).

Although one can find a way to optimise them as well like, for instance, assigning an identification number to each categorical option, it's often not recommended due to the straightforwardness of their role in neural networks, meaning that it can be even counterproductive to optimise them.

MLP Dynamics

Now that we have just described the essential components of our MLP neural network, we can get to explain how this apparently simple algorithm actually works, ultimately allowing us to predict the emotional content of a certain audio file given its feature matrix.

We'll do this by setting up a relatively simple and representative example: let's say that we have extracted all features from an audio database of 100 songs (Feature Engineering) and also have selected the 50 best ones according to the emotional annotations for arousal and valence in each audio file (Feature Selection). Thus, we have a feature matrix of size [100 files x 50 features] (for our input layer) and a target matrix of size [100 files x 2 emotional dimensions] (for our output layer). Also, we've decided that we'll have one hidden layer of 75 neurons, the bias constant will be zero and we'll be using sigmoid activation functions for both the hidden layer and the output layer (logistic regression).

Once we have these, we proceed to explain the dynamics of one iteration of the neural network (which is not the same as an epoch, as we will see):

1. Pre-Processing[23]

- (a) Each column in the **feature matrix** (input) should be *standardised*, meaning that it has to have an arithmetic mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. This is achieved by subtracting the mean value of the column to all the elements in it and then dividing by their original standard deviation. This is done to better organise the data without destroying their relative relationship.
- (b) Each column in the **target matrix** (output) must be *normalised*, meaning that it has to have a maximum value of 1 and a minimum value of zero.

As the values for both arousal and valence are positive, this is achieved by simply dividing by the maximum value of the column in evaluation. This is done to actually compare the sigmoid outputs (normalised) in the this layer (predictions) with the actual emotional annotations.

- (c) Define the **hyper-parameters** and **parameters** of the MLP neural network.
- (d) Initialise the **weight matrices** by generating random numbers normally distributed in each one. In order to connect the input layer with the hidden layer, we'll make a weight matrix of size [50 features x 75 hidden neurons]. To connect the hidden layer with the output layer, following the same logic, we'll build a second weight matrix of [75 hidden neurons x 2 emotions].
- (e) Initialise the **bias vectors** by creating two vectors of zeros, in this case, to be added to the operations. These will be of size [1 x 75 hidden neurons], complementing the first weight matrix, and of [1 x 2 emotions], complementing the second one.

2. Training[21]

- (a) In order to train the MLP neural network, we **take one** feature vector of size [1 file x 50 features] from the feature matrix and one vector of size [1 file x 2 emotions] from the target matrix. This training method that learns from one audio file at a time is called *Online Training* and it has been proven to outperform the alternative method (*Batch Training*) when dealing with numerous inputs.
- (b) **Forward Propagation:** The matrices are multiplied from left to right, being added the bias term and applied the activation function in each neuron. The input layer multiplies the first weight layer ($[1 \times 50][50 \times 75] = [1 \times 75]$), the first bias vector is added ($[1 \times 75] + [1 \times 75] = [1 \times 75]$) and the correspondent activation function (sigmoid in this case) is applied to the final result for each of the 75 numbers now in the hidden layer's neurons. Then, the same process is repeated for the propagation of data from the hidden layer to the output layer: $[1 \times 75][75 \times 2] = [1 \times 2]$, $[1 \times 2] + [1 \times 2] = [1 \times 2]$, and finally applying the activation function (also sigmoid) to the result. This last [1x2] matrix that we've obtained is our prediction. These calculations can be written in the following manner:

$$Z_2 = X \cdot W_1 + B_1 \quad (2.31)$$

$$H = \sigma(Z_2) \quad (2.32)$$

$$Z_3 = H \cdot W_2 + B_2 \quad (2.33)$$

$$\hat{Y} = \sigma(Z_3) \quad (2.34)$$

where the W s represent the first and second weight matrices, the B s represent the first and second bias vectors, the Z s are the pre-processed hidden and output layers, H stores the values of the hidden layer and \hat{Y} stores the values of our final prediction for the output layer. The numbers in the subindexes reference the layer to which each of the variables belongs (1 = input layer, 2 = hidden layer, 3 = output layer).

- (c) After the forward pass, we obtain the prediction values for both arousal and valence, stored in the vector \hat{Y} [1x2]. These generally won't be equal to the real values of the arousal and valence for that audio file, which are stored in the target vector Y [1x2]. Hence, in order to start correcting the weights in the weight matrices, we have to calculate the **error** between the target values in Y and the predicted values in \hat{Y} . We can use different metrics like the *absolute difference* ($|Y - \hat{Y}|$) or the *square error* ($0.5 \cdot (Y - \hat{Y})^2$). As we are dealing with normalised outputs (from 0 to 1) we would preferably use an error function (also known as cost function) that can perform well in this range. In this way, *cross-entropy* error seems like a good choice for this particular case, as we're dealing with probabilities (sigmoid activation functions) and its expression ($-Y \cdot \log(\hat{Y}) - (1 - Y) \cdot \log(1 - \hat{Y})$) implies a binary interaction between the variables.
- (d) **Backpropagation:** This is the core process of the learning algorithm in the MLP neural network. From the recently calculated error, we will derive two matrices ∂W_1 and ∂W_2 , which have the same size of W_1 and W_2 respectively, that store the updates for each value in the weight matrices. In order to do that, we'll calculate the partial derivative of the error with respect to each of the weight matrices applying the chain rule wisely and, as a result, moving backward all the way to the very input vector. The process could be summarised with the following sequence of equations:

$$\partial W_1 = \frac{\partial E}{\partial W_2} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial \hat{Y}} \cdot \frac{\partial \hat{Y}}{\partial Z_3} \cdot \frac{\partial Z_3}{\partial W_2} \quad (2.35)$$

$$\partial W_2 = \frac{\partial E}{\partial W_1} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial \hat{Y}} \cdot \frac{\partial \hat{Y}}{\partial Z_3} \cdot \frac{\partial Z_3}{\partial H} \cdot \frac{\partial H}{\partial Z_2} \cdot \frac{\partial Z_2}{\partial W_1} \quad (2.36)$$

where E is the error function. Calculating these partial derivatives along with the expressions of the forward propagation phase, we can arrive at the

following expressions:

$$\partial W_1 = H^T \cdot ((\hat{Y} - Y) \cdot \sigma'(Z_3)) \quad (2.37)$$

$$\partial W_2 = X^T \cdot ((\hat{Y} - Y) \cdot \sigma'(Z_3) \cdot W_2^T \cdot \sigma'(Z_2)) \quad (2.38)$$

which ultimately gives us these ∂W_1 and ∂W_2 matrices. There, $\sigma'(x) = \sigma(x) \cdot (1 - \sigma(x))$. Note that these expressions above are particular for every error function, and in our case we happen to have $\hat{Y} - Y$ as the partial derivative of our error function with respect to \hat{Y} .

- (e) Once we achieve backpropagation, we may be tempted to subtract these new matrices to the weight matrices directly. This approach is very problematic, as instead of minimizing the error little by little in a progressive way we may most probably bounce between the increasing and the decreasing of the error unpredictably within each iteration (not necessarily epoch). In order to avoid that, we're going to **update** the weight matrices by taking a usually small percentage of both ∂W_1 and ∂W_2 and adding it up to a usually large percentage of the previous little percentage of ∂W_1 and ∂W_2 . This is better schematised in the following pair of equations:

$$UPD_n = \eta \cdot \partial W_n + \mu \cdot UPD_n \quad (2.39)$$

$$W_n = W_n - UPD_n \quad (2.40)$$

where UPD is the final update term, $n = 1, 2$, η is the learning rate and μ is the momentum of the neural network.

- (f) Finally, once having updated both weight matrices, we're ready to receive the next input vector of size [1x50] (for the second song in the list) and its correspondent target vector of size [1x2]. If we **repeat** the process for all 100 audio files in the database, that would make one epoch and, having passed through all the specified epochs, we can use the final weight matrices W_1 and W_2 to predict the emotional content of the songs. But... would they perform well? How can we know for sure?

3. Testing, Validation and Regularization

- (a) The process of **testing** refers, in our case, to the prediction of the emotional content of similar audio files that hasn't been used in the training process detailed above and seeing how well the performance goes. These predictions are simply done by taking the final learned weight matrices W_1 and W_2 ,

feeding the new data into the neural network and applying a quick and normal forward propagation. Then, one can calculate the mean error of the predictions and evaluate it in different metrics to get an idea of how powerful is the retrieved algorithm. In case only one database is studied, one can *split* the dataset into a learning subset (usually from 80 to 90 percent of the database) to use exclusively for training the neural network and a testing one (usually from 10 to 20 percent of the database) to use exclusively for testing the neural network. This approach, nevertheless, is often inconclusive when judging the actual potentiality of the trained neural network: something as simple as the order of the inputs or the consequential equilibrium of similarities between the chosen learning subset and the testing subset can result in getting the wrong evaluation. One of the approaches to subtly caring about the quality of the final testing results during the training process consists in testing the performance of the neural network after every epoch (with the actual testing subset) and stopping the neural network's learning process if this testing error (not the learning error!) rises, as it's supposed to go down with each epoch. This is called *early stopping* [24] and has proven to be very handy for splitting experiments.

- (b) The process of **Validation**, on the other hand, refers to the careful estimation of how accurately our neural network will really perform in practice. There is one very well known approach for this part called *cross-validation* [25]. This divides the dataset in k different subsets of equal quantity of elements (folds) and performs learning and testing with all of them, averaging the experiments results at the end. For example, if one wants to perform a 10 fold cross-validation, one must divide the dataset into 10 parts and run 10 independent learning and testing experiments, involving 9 of the folds in the training phase and 1 in the testing phase, and alternating between them in each experiment so that, at the end of the 10th one, all ten folds have participated in the testing phase. The results derived from this method have been proven to be far more representative of the dataset than any splitting task, and its implementation is almost always a 'must do' in MIR studies.
- (c) The process of **Regularization** [26], finally, deals directly with the problem of *overfitting* in the training phase. If the data is fitted harshly with high order polynomials the testing results would be quite unsatisfactory, for the algorithm isn't interested in generalising to data outside the learning subset anymore: it's interested in excelling in the fitting of this learning subset, which in the end proves to be absolutely counterproductive. To avoid this overfitting problem, we can penalise the weight matrices if they appear to

be fitting the data too much. This is called *weight decay* and it's achieved by introducing a new term to the error function:

$$E = E + \frac{\lambda}{2} \cdot \sum_n \text{tr}(W_n^T \cdot W_n) \quad (2.41)$$

where λ is the regularization parameter and *tr* indicates the trace operation. Consequentially, one must adapt the weight calculation expressions by introducing the derivative of this new term with respect to the weight matrices W_1 and W_2 in order to do backpropagation correctly, as $\partial W_n = \frac{\partial E}{\partial W_n}$ and the expression of E has this new term. As $\text{tr}(W_n^T \cdot W_n)$ is equal to the sum of all the elements of W_n squared, we can treat it as $W_n \odot W_n$ (although these matrices not of the same size, as it's not a square matrix), where \odot denotes the element-wise product or Hadamard product. Hence, the correction of the backpropagation algorithm would simply be:

$$dW_n = dW_n + \frac{\partial\left(\frac{\lambda}{2} \cdot (W_n \odot W_n)\right)}{\partial W_n} = dW_n + \lambda \cdot W_n \quad (2.42)$$

Initialising the regularization parameter λ around the order of 10^{-4} has proven to be a good starting point to see improvements in the testing results. This technique of regularization is recommended to be used along with cross-validation, because if its parameter λ is too high, we also can end up *underfitting* the mapping. One can only see the neural network performance objectively by using validation techniques.

Once understood the learning and testing processes of the MLP neural network, we can start making predictions automatically by choosing some values for the hyper-parameters (learning rate, momentum, number of hidden neurons... etc) but... are they the best ones we can use? Most surely not, and that's what the fourth and final part of the process (*Model Selection*) will deal with.

Right now, we are able to play around with both regression and classification with the first database (2.1.1) and second database (2.1.2) respectively. Classification (binary) works in the same way as regression, but rounding up the results to 0 or to 1 or even applying an additional softmax activation function to the output layer. This MLP neural network proves to be an effective method when mapping audio features to static emotional annotations. In the next section, we'll take a look at a more advanced neural network model that will allow us to map data sequentially and, thus, analyse dynamic emotional annotations.

Figure 2.6: This figure shows how the MLP neural network learns over time, as the learning error derived by adjusting the weights falls exponentially over the epochs.

2.4.2 The RNN-LSTM

The Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Network (RNN-LSTM) [22] is a very successful model in text generation tasks that allows the user to retrieve a map of dynamic annotations, where the time sequence matters. Therefore, this time we won't need to capture the temporal dynamics of each audio file by applying statistical descriptors to the LLD vectors: we feed these last ones to the RNN-LSTM directly.

As we will see, this process takes a great amount of time considering the performance duration of the static model (MLP); which seems right, as we'll be dealing with the three-dimensional LLD matrix and also be implementing a more sophisticated framework in order to provide the neural network with memory. If one has understood the basic MLP logic, one will find the current approach to be just a refined extension of the already learned foundations.

RNNs and the Problem of Gradient Vanishing

A Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is a particular implementation of this machine learning tool that's able to process data sequentially; i.e, the performance of the algorithm for one input vector will depend on the performances that came before it with previous input vectors [28].

The way in which this was initially thought to be accomplished consisted in adding up a certain percentage of the hidden layer of the previous iteration to the hidden layer

pertaining to the current iteration. In this way, recurrent neural networks can store information in the current hidden layer that 'invokes' both the inputs and hidden units of the previous iterations; thus implementing an implicit memory system in the neural network.

Nevertheless, there have been several issues with this particular approach to memory building, being the most notable one the so called *Vanishing Gradient* problem. This causes the derivatives in the backpropagation phase to become either zero (and not correcting the weights anymore, in consequence) or infinity (and cause the weight matrices to become infinite). This last case is sometimes referred to as the *Exploding Gradient* problem. This issue makes basic RNNs practically impossible to train in a sufficiently complex environment.

This strong limitation went on until, in 1997, the Long Short-Term Memory unit (LSTM) was created [22] in an attempt to solve this very problem and finally succeeded, bringing a dramatic improvement in the algorithms and even, one could say, causing an important paradigm shift in machine learning by finally establishing the neural network models as highly relevant to the field.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

As stated in the paragraph above, the LSTM units were created in 1997 by ... in order to solve the Vanishing Gradient problem in RNNs. They are logical pieces of code that manage the recurrent data in a way that resembles human's memory dynamics.

The logic behind these LSTM units can be resumed in the interactions between its parts, which are:

- **Input Gate** (To which degree should I *write* in the memory?)
- **Forget Gate** (To which degree should I *forget* what I have already stored in the memory?)
- **Output Gate** (To which degree should I just *read* the inputs without writing at all in the memory?)
- **State** (What do I actually *store* at the moment in the memory?)

These gating dynamics are what ultimately allow us to store data in the LSTM recurrently and therefore provide our RNN with memory. As with the MLP neural network for static annotations, here we also have some forward propagation and backpropagation in the training phase and, while these processes follow the same

Figure 2.7: Scheme showing the architecture of an LSTM cell. a_t , i_t , f_t and o_t are the input activation, input, forget and output gates respectively, C_t is the current state of the cell, and $Pred_t$ refers to the current predicted values for this LSTM unit.

Figure 2.8: Scheme showing the basic architecture of a single layer RNN-LSTM. This is the model we'll work with when predicting emotions one by one.

underlying steps, the rather idiosyncratic architecture of the LSTM cells makes it more complex.

This time, though, we'll feed the three dimensional LLD matrix [files x frames x LLD] directly to the LSTM layout. For each analysed audio file in the database, we'll get its correspondent two-dimensional matrix [frames x LLD]. There will be, then, two types of inputs: the *sequential* and the *static* inputs. The sequential types are the

ones upon which the LSTM will build the recurrence relations; in our case, these will be the frames, as they're the time units of the analysed audio file. The static types, conversely, are the ones that can be properly called 'inputs', as they are analogous to the MLP neural network inputs; in our case, these will be our 80 LLDs.

Once we have preprocessed the variables in the same fasion as in the MLP neural network (section 2.4.1), we can take one audio file at a time and do forward propagation:

$$z_t^a = W_a \cdot X_t + U_a \cdot Pred_{t-1} + B_a \quad (2.43)$$

$$a_t = \tanh(z_t^a) \quad (2.44)$$

$$z_t^i = W_i \cdot X_t + U_i \cdot Pred_{t-1} + B_i \quad (2.45)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(z_t^i) \quad (2.46)$$

$$z_t^f = W_f \cdot X_t + U_f \cdot Pred_{t-1} + B_f \quad (2.47)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(z_t^f) \quad (2.48)$$

$$z_t^o = W_o \cdot X_t + U_o \cdot Pred_{t-1} + B_o \quad (2.49)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(z_t^o) \quad (2.50)$$

$$C_t = a_t \odot i_t + f_t \odot C_{t-1} \quad (2.51)$$

$$Pred_t = \tanh(C_t) \odot o_t \quad (2.52)$$

where

$$W = [W_a; W_i; W_f; W_o] \quad (2.53)$$

$$U = [U_a; U_i; U_f; U_o] \quad (2.54)$$

are the *weight matrix* W and the *recurrence weight matrix* U respectively and

$$B = [B_a; B_i; B_f; B_o] \quad (2.55)$$

is the *bias vector*. Using $g = a, i, f, o$ as a general notation for the four gates, the parameters z_t^g would be the pre-activated gates (relevant when organising backpropagation) of the analysed frame t , g_t are the gates themselves, C_t is the state of the LSTM and $Pred_t$ are the final predictions derived from the LSTM's forward propagation. Also, \tanh references the hyperbolic tangent function and σ the sigmoid (logistic) function.

Once we have derived these parameters, we get as many error measures as audio frames were analysed (and fed to the RNN-LSTM) for the analysed file. Hence, we can start backpropagating sequentially from the last analysed frame to the first. It's highly convenient for this particular case of backpropagation to be scrupulously organised in order not to make a single mistake that could ultimately compromise the LSTMs performance, as there appear to be many parameters that, although some of them share the same nature, one might easily get lost in the task. This can be done starting with the derivative of the error in the prediction $\delta Pred_t$ and deriving the rest of the terms from this one:

$$\delta Pred_t = \frac{\partial E}{\partial Pred_t} \quad (2.56)$$

Once we have this term, we are able to calculate the gradients below by newly applying the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial o_t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial Pred_t} \cdot \frac{\partial Pred_t}{\partial o_t} = \delta Pred_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \quad (2.57)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial C_t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial Pred_t} \cdot \frac{\partial Pred_t}{\partial C_t} = \delta Pred_t \odot o_t \odot (1 - \tanh(C_t)) \quad (2.58)$$

Now that we have $\frac{\partial E}{\partial C_t}$, to which will be added the term $\frac{\partial E}{\partial C_{t-1}}$ for to accumulate the gradient recurrently for the LSTMs' state, we may continue and calculate the gradients of the functions related to it:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial i_t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial C_t} \cdot \frac{\partial C_t}{\partial i_t} = \delta C_t \odot a_t \quad (2.59)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial f_t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial C_t} \cdot \frac{\partial C_t}{\partial f_t} = \delta C_t \odot C_{t-1} \quad (2.60)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial C_{t-1}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial C_t} \cdot \frac{\partial C_t}{\partial C_{t-1}} = \delta C_t \odot f_t \quad (2.61)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial a_t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial C_t} \cdot \frac{\partial C_t}{\partial a_t} = \delta C_t \odot i_t \quad (2.62)$$

Now that we have the derivatives of our gates in place, we have to get the derivatives of the pre-activated gates, that are the ones that directly depend on all W , U and B , which we have finally to update.

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial z_t^i} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial i_t} \cdot \frac{\partial i_t}{\partial z_t^i} = \delta C_t \odot a_t \odot \tanh'(i_t) = \delta C_t \odot a_t \odot (1 - \tanh^2(a_t)) \quad (2.63)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial z_t^f} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial f_t} \cdot \frac{\partial f_t}{\partial z_t^f} = \delta C_t \odot C_{t-1} \odot \sigma'(f_t) = \delta C_t \odot C_{t-1} \odot f_t \odot (1 - f_t) \quad (2.64)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial z_t^a} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial a_t} \cdot \frac{\partial a_t}{\partial z_t^a} = \delta C_t \odot i_t \odot \sigma'(a_t) = \delta C_t \odot i_t \odot a_t \odot (1 - a_t) \quad (2.65)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial z_t^o} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial o_t} \cdot \frac{\partial o_t}{\partial z_t^o} = \delta \text{Pred}_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \odot \sigma'(o_t) = \delta \text{Pred}_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \odot o_t \odot (1 - o_t) \quad (2.66)$$

where $\sigma'(x) = \sigma(x) \cdot (1 - \sigma(x))$ is the expression of the derivative of the sigmoid function and $\tanh'(x) = (1 - \tanh^2(x))$ is the expression of the derivative of the hyperbolic tangent function.

As we finish backpropagating across all frames from the end to the beginning, we can immediately calculate the deltas of our weight matrices and bias vector in order to update them. For that, we apply the following logic:

$$\delta W = \sum_{t=0}^T \delta G_t \otimes X_t \quad (2.67)$$

$$\delta U = \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \delta G_{t+1} \otimes \text{Pred}_t \quad (2.68)$$

$$\delta B = \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \delta G_{t+1} \quad (2.69)$$

Finally, we can proceed and update our weights and biases:

$$W = W - \eta \cdot \delta W \quad (2.70)$$

$$U = U - \eta \cdot \delta U \quad (2.71)$$

$$B = B - \eta \cdot \delta B \quad (2.72)$$

where the parameter η is the *learning rate* of the process. It's very important to note that the learning rate parameter, for this particular model, needs to start at a fairly high value (around 0.1 in our case) and be reduced after each epoch in order to effectively learn from the data. This epoch-dependant regularization of the learning rate can be easily achieved by defining the learning rate as follows:

$$\eta(\text{epoch}) = \frac{\eta_0}{1 + \frac{\text{epoch}}{m}} \quad (2.73)$$

where η_0 is the initial learning rate (constant), *epoch* is the current epoch number and m acts as a regularization parameter.

Hence, with the help of this advanced model of neural network (the RNN-LSTM), we're now able to analyse sequential data, which is wonderful in order to make sense of the characteristic dynamic annotations in the Emotion in Music Database (2.1.3). It's also important to note that the annotations in this dataset are given each half a second and our analysis frames for retrieving the LLDs are only 25ms in length. In order to work this out, we'll **interpolate** between the values of the annotations so to match the time interval between frames.

2.5 Model Selection

So far, we've extracted a great number of audio features and low level descriptors from some databases in 2.2, then selected the most relevant ones by applying the CFS method in 2.3 and, finally, we've built our three models of neural networks (MLP regressor, MLP classifier and RNN-LSTM regressor) in 2.4. Now that we have everything in order, we can confidently get to the final phase of the Music Information Retrieval process: *model selection*. However, one must note that this last section is not mandatory for the MIR task to be done (neither feature selection is), but it's proven to be very useful if one really wants to build a machine learning algorithm that retrieves the best results possible.

All neural networks have hyper-parameters on which their very performance

depends. In order to get the best model, one must optimise it and, in our case with neural networks, the chance is presented with the possibility of fine-tuning these hyper-parameters.

For the first (2.1.1) and the second (2.1.2) databases (MLP neural network), we have the following hyper-parameters to optimise:

- Number of selected features
- Number of hidden layers
- Number of neurons in each hidden layer
- Learning rate
- Momentum
- Regularization parameter

For the third (2.1.3) database (RNN-LSTM neural network), due to its long computation time and lack of loose parameters that we can tune, we have the following hyper-parameters to optimise:

- Learning rate
- Parameter 'm' for learning rate decay

In order to select good models for our three neural networks, there's a very intuitive method that one can use and that is guaranteed to have, if not the best result possible, certainly one of the bests depending on how it's constructed: the *grid search* method. This consists in making a vector of possible values for each hyper-parameter and trying out all possible combinations of the elements of these vectors. The combination that gives us the best result, once run the neural network with all of them, is the right model to choose. Although it should generally give the best model, it becomes notably inefficient when there are too many hyper-parameters to optimise. For instance, we should run the MLP neural network around ten million times if we want to do grid search. That would take months on a fairly fast computer! Clearly not the way to go for the MLP model, though it can be used for the selection of the right RNN-LSTM model, as there are only two hyper-parameters to optimise and the number of possible combinations between the elements of their vectors doesn't usually reach the hundred.

In both cases, though, we've decided to deviate a little from this grid search in order not to spend that much time looking for the best models and apply a second alternative: the *random search* method [27]. This one also requires the creation of vectors with

some possible values of each hyper-parameter, but instead of going through all the possibilities it selects a small number of random combinations and runs the neural network with them to see which gives the best performance. Although one could firstly think that this method is a lazy shortcut to avoiding the efficiency problem with the grid search method (which, in a way, it surely appears to be so), it's one of the most (if not the most) used model selection methods due to its straightforwardness, easiness, quickness and, maybe somewhat counterintuitively, its accuracy.

To see this last point more clearly, we can take the case of optimising the two parameters in the RNN-LSTM for the third database. These are the initial learning rate λ_0 and the parameter m , responsible for its decay through the epochs. If we represent the vector of possible values of each of these parameters as dimensions in a plane, we can represent the combinations between these possible values as points in that plane. Then, one can include the *result* variable in the demonstration and make the space tridimensional, so that we can have a function that depends on these three variables and search for its minimum (the result variable is an error in a regression), which coincides with the best performance of the neural network.

As this is a search in a three dimensional space, one might draw the analogy of two pirates searching a treasure in an island for one day and, in case none of them can find it, the one that's been closer to it gets it. One of them is very meticulous and goes step-by-step, searching exhaustively in an area before moving to the next one (does grid search), and the other one jumps to random places in the island and looks if it is there (does random search). One can see that at the end of the day the one holding this last strategy is far more likely to get the treasure.

Hence, random search would be the preferred method to do model selection with.

Chapter 3

Results

The main part of the project has been focused on the methodology itself, building a set of different nature functions and algorithms that allow us to perform an MIR task while understanding everything we're doing at a fundamental level. This next part is meant to show some results from the feature selection phase of the project, the model selection one and from the experiments that were carried out to test the neural networks' performance.

3.1 Model Verification: The Hidden Fifth Step

Coding neural networks can be very tricky and challenging if not enough scrupulosity is placed in the process. A single malfunctioning piece of code can make the algorithms fall apart, and no relevant predictions could ever be derived from such a system in most of the cases. For that reason, there exist several methods of making sure that the machine learning algorithms work properly and, in the case of neural networks, we can also apply a particular one that can quantify its degree of accuracy. These are the following:

- **The Ideal Sample Method:** This is the simplest, most intuitive and most elegant method to prove that a machine learning algorithm is actually doing its job in a general way. It consists in building both a constant input matrix and a constant output matrix and feeding them to the neural network. As the same inputs always give the same outputs, one can expect almost perfect predictions from the algorithm; and in case they're not obtained that's sufficient proof that something is not working as it should be.
- **The Random Sample Method:** As the input features are generally correlated with the output emotions in some way, one might expect the neural network to perform significantly poorer when having to make sense of random data for both inputs and outputs. If this is not the case, though, it doesn't necessarily mean

that the problem is in the algorithm, as it can also be in the experimental setup or even in the negligible correlation between inputs and outputs for the task at hand. In any case, it's a useful test to run if one wants to see whether the process is effective in the task at hand or not.

- **The Gradient Checking Method:** This is by far the most reliable method for checking that everything is in place inside the backpropagation algorithm, which is arguably the hardest and most sensible piece of code in the neural network. In the original backpropagation sequence, we calculate the partial derivative of the error with respect to the weight matrices by applying the chain rule (very fast method), but one can achieve approximately the same result by calculating this partial derivation by the *finite differences* method. This last one is based on the principle that if we perturb a single weight in a matrix ever so slightly a quantity ϵ twice (addition and subtraction), perform forward propagation (prediction) with them, calculate the error and then subtract them and divide by twice the parameter ϵ , we end up getting a fairly decent approximation of the derivative of the error with respect to that perturbed single weight in the matrix. By comparing these two results (the one obtained by the chain rule in backpropagation and this approximation by finite differences) we can state confidently that our neural network is doing (or not) backpropagation correctly.

We present the results of these tests in the tables below, which provide a preview of the actual results for the experiments. These in table 3.1 are done with the same parameters but different types of inputs and outputs accordingly. We've split the database in two groups: 85% for the learning set and the remaining 15% for the testing one. 5 epochs have been run for the RNN-LSTM's experiments and 100 for the MLP's. The errors are shown as the regression's error percentage (derived by the normalised absolute difference between the predicted values and the actual test outputs), except for the gradient checking method, which is equal to the expression in the following equation:

$$Error = \frac{norm(\delta W_{BP} - \delta W_{GC})}{norm(\delta W_{BP} + \delta W_{GC})} \quad (3.1)$$

where δW_{BP} is the result derived from backpropagation, δW_{GC} is the one derived from gradient checking by the finite differences method and *norm* references the Euclidean norm of a matrix. In order to prove that the backpropagation algorithm's chain derivation works, this error has to lie around 10^{-8} for normalised inputs and outputs, although little to none literature has been found that can explain why this happens to be the norm or even if an actual consensus was reached at all. The shown result was derived from the averaging of the errors for two weight matrices across ten independent checkings.

Table 3.1: Results for Model Verification techniques (using regression tasks in the arousal dimension). Gradient checking has only been applied to the MLP neural network.

Neural Network	Original	Ideal	Random	Gradient Checking
MLP	15.23%	0.22%	25.81%	1.45e-10
RNN-LSTM	19.52%	0.07%	20.56%	-

As we can see in the tables, both the MLP and the RNN-LSTM have passed the ideal sample test, as the error derived from these processes is significantly lower than the usual error. This is the most important result, as it demonstrates that both neural networks are doing their job and can be used in further experiments. Also, the MLP has also passed the gradient checking test and its results for the random sample are significantly worse than for the original sample (actual extracted features). Nevertheless, attending to the results extracted from the random sample for the RNN-LSTM and from the original sample, we can appreciate that the numbers are really close, meaning that the gathered data doesn't appear to be relevant to the task at hand. We'll see in further sections of this chapter if this is true or it just had to pass the model selection phase in order to get optimal results for the original sample.

3.2 Feature Selection for MLP Regression

In this section, we annotate the top five best features (composed by an LLD and a statistical functional applied to it) for arousal (table 3.2), valence (table 3.3) and both dimensions analysed together (table 3.4).

By looking at them, it stands out that all of the selected LLD in the top five happen to be deltas (derivatives of actual LLD vectors). This is a quite intriguing and interesting result, as it means that it's not the actual change of these LLD in time what matters the most when predicting emotions: it's actually their sensitivity to change what does. And although no piece of literature that corroborates this phenomenon has been found by the author, one could informally assert that this actually makes sense from an introspective point of view, as it seems that this velocity (and even acceleration) in the appearance of the stimulus has the most to say when judging emotional reactions.

One can also see that spectral features dominate the tables, with special mention to the *spectral slope* for arousal (correlated with the amount of irregularities in the spectrum), *low-mid range energy* for valence and both emotions (that's generally more soothing and pleasurable than in the high range of the spectrum) and finally it's

Table 3.2: Top five best features (LLD and SF) for Arousal dimension

Rank	Low Level Descriptor (LLD)	Statistical Functional (SF)
1	Spectral Flux (Delta)	Relative Duration 25%
2	Spectral Slope (Delta)	Relative Duration 25%
3	Spectral Slope (Delta)	Relative Duration of Positive Curvature
4	Spectral Energy RMS (Delta)	Relative Duration 25%
5	Spectral Slope (Delta)	Relative Duration 50%

Table 3.3: Top five best features (LLD and SF) for Valence dimension

Rank	Low Level Descriptor (LLD)	Statistical Functional (SF)
1	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 4
2	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 5
3	6th MFCC (Delta)	LPC 2
4	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 3
5	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 2

also worth mentioning the *spectral flux* for arousal and both emotions (instantaneous spectral changes throughout the music extract).

3.3 Neural Networks' Hyper-Parameters Selection

We've performed random search differently depending on the neural network we're studying, as their performance durations aren't close at all, being the average duration of an RNN-LSTM task with the third database (dynamic annotations) from thirty to fifty times greater than the average of an MLP task (static annotations).

With this in mind, the author of the present project decided to run the following three preliminary experiments (**Model Selection**):

- For the **MLP**, the model selection for both static regression and classification consisted in running *2000 times* independent *10 fold cross-validation* tasks with

Table 3.4: Top five best features (LLD and SF) for both Emotions plane

Rank	Low Level Descriptor (LLD)	Statistical Functional (SF)
1	Spectral Flux (Delta)	Relative Duration 25%
2	Spectral Energy RMS (Delta)	Relative Duration 25%
3	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 4
4	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 5
5	Spectral Energy 250-650 Hz (Delta)	LPC 3

Table 3.5: MLP's top three best hyper-parameters and their result for the Arousal dimension. η is the learning rate, μ is the momentum, λ is the regularization parameter and 'HL' stands for 'Hidden Layers'.

Result	η	μ	λ	% Features	N HL	N Neurons in HL
13.47%	0.012	0.86	0.00210	3.0%	1	[31]
14.02%	0.004	0.92	0.00130	2.8%	2	[31,62]
14.04%	0.012	0.86	0.00045	1.2%	2	[124,31]

100 epochs for each fold and the *absolute difference* as the metric of the result (error).

- For the **RNN-LSTM**, the model selection for dynamic regression consisted in running 15 times independent 2 fold *cross-validation* tasks with 5 epochs for each fold and the *absolute difference* as the metric of the result (error).

All results for all combinations of hyper-parameters' values in both experiments were saved. Having the results from these previous random selection process, the best three combinations were abstracted from the experiments' results and then run the following confirmation procedures (**Model Performance**):

- For each top three best combinations in regression and the top one in classification using the **MLP**, we run another 100 times a 10 fold *cross-validation* task with 100 epochs for each fold and the *absolute difference* as the metric of the result (error) for regression and *percentage of correctly classified items* for classification. We averaged the errors to have the final mean result.
- For the top best combination (only one) in regression using the **RNN-LSTM**, we run another 2 times a 10 fold *cross-validation* task with 5 epochs for each fold and the *absolute difference* as the metric of the result (error). We averaged the errors to have the final mean result.

The results from above's studies are displayed in the tables 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7 in regression and table 3.8 in classification for the static model (MLP neural network) and 3.9 for the dynamic model. As our particular RNN-LSTM architecture cannot take more than one type of output, results are shown only in arousal and valence independently for the dynamic model.

3.3.1 MLP Hyper-Parameters Selection and Results

We can see that the results derived from the MLP neural network in regression (static) for the soundtrack dataset can let us know the arousal and valence of a song with some certainty. If we feed the neural network with an input matrix full of random numbers,

Table 3.6: MLP’s top three best hyper-parameters and their result for the Valence dimension. η is the learning rate, μ is the momentum, λ is the regularization parameter and ‘HL’ stands for ‘Hidden Layers’.

Result	η	μ	λ	% Features	N HL	N Neurons in HL
19.37%	0.002	0.96	0.00065	1.4%	3	[125,25,50]
19.84%	0.002	0.94	0.00180	2.2%	2	[75,75]
20.36%	0.002	0.98	0.00095	1.0%	2	[100,25]

Table 3.7: MLP’s top three best hyper-parameters and their result for the Emotions plane. η is the learning rate, μ is the momentum, λ is the regularization parameter and ‘HL’ stands for ‘Hidden Layers’.

Result	η	μ	λ	% Features	N HL	N Neurons in HL
14.49%	0.004	0.94	0.00010	1.8%	2	[62,31]
15.01%	0.010	0.88	0.00085	1.4%	2	[93,31]
15.11%	0.006	0.96	0.00180	3.0%	3	[93,62,31]

as discussed in section 3.1, the errors we get usually oscillate between 25% and 30%, meaning that the feature sets have some relevance to the task, as their derived errors (13.47%, 19.37% and 14.49%) are significantly smaller in general.

We might also appreciate that the neural network has special difficulty classifying valence compared to arousal and both emotions at the same time. This struggle is obvious by observing the top three values for the learning rate and momentum, which are significantly lower and higher respectively than the ones appearing in both arousal and the combination of these emotional dimensions. This means that the neural network functions more conservatively during the task, keeping the previous weight updates with its high momentum and changing them very little with its low learning rate.

Having a look now to the results for the binary classification task, we can see that, although the model performs well with other datasets, the unevenly distributed data that conforms the input sets (there are far more non-calm songs than calm ones) makes it rather difficult for the neural network to escape the temptation of performing *ZeroR* pseudo-classification. This simple technique (ZeroR) is used in order to discriminate

Table 3.8: MLP best hyper-parameters’ combination and their result for Calmness (binary classification). η is the learning rate, μ is the momentum, λ is the regularization parameter and ‘HL’ stands for ‘Hidden Layers’.

Class	Result	ZeroR	η	μ	λ	% Feat.	N HL	N in HL
Calm	79,75 %	76,25 %	0.184	0.82	0.002	3.6%	3	[30,15,30]

Table 3.9: RNN-LSTM's best hyper-parameters' combination and their result for the Arousal and Valence dimensions. η is the learning rate and m is the learning rate decay parameter.

Type	Result	η	m
Arousal	18.20%	0.025	1.8
Valence	20.49%	0.025	1.8

the actual relevance of a binary classification's final result, and it works by always predicting the class with the most ones. For example, if a certain dataset has 70 'No' and 30 'Yes' then, the ZeroR pseudo-classifier will always predict 'No' and end up with a 70% of accuracy without doing any kind of mapping or extrapolation from the dataset.

In our case, the result for the ZeroR classifier and the one for the actual MLP classifier are very close in magnitude meaning that, although the result that the neural network gives us might appear quite good at first glance, it really isn't that impressive at all. This problem might be effectively solved by applying some kind of misclassification extra penalty in the minority class within the MLP's architecture, so to make it more sensitive and careful when deciding on challenging mappings.

3.3.2 RNN-LSTM Hyper-Parameters Selection and Results

By looking at the final results for the RNN-LSTM neural network, one may realise that the result for valence is almost equal to the one derived from the random sample in 3.1. Also, the result for the arousal dimension, although better than its neighbor, doesn't stand out either, and still stays fairly close to the random sample's result.

This appears to tell us that the gathered data, the LLD matrix, has nothing better to say than a random matrix, but we know that this conclusion is most likely to be false. If that's the case, then... what happened? Well, many possible things could have occurred for these mediocre results to precipitate, but the most probable one is an error in the fundamental setup for the experiment. It's possible that working with analysis frames of 25ms and interpolated emotional annotations also each 25ms is not a good idea, as this time lapse is way too short for the neural network to properly learn from. A mini-batch learning approach (splitting the frames into different analysis groups) could solve this problem, as well as not interpolate between annotations and work with actual features describing each second or half a second.

Furthermore, the implemented model of the RNN-LSTM for this project is a basic one, lacking regularization, multiple possible layers and with no pre-training phase to let the LSTMs 'warm up' before the actual task. Building a more complex model and

preventing overfitting by regularization would be the next steps towards a successful dynamic mapping.

3.4 A Simple Destabiliser

So far, we've discussed several results that, in the case of the MLP neural network in regression, lead to what appeared to be nice results. But... are we really classifying emotions? What one means by asking that rather puzzling and intriguing question is that we're possibly lost in a forest of parameters where non spotted independent variables can easily get in the way without us ever knowing of them. They can even propagate back to the annotations procedure when building the very databases! At first glance, it appears to be quite a challenge to determine if we're doing Automatic Emotion Recognition properly; the truth is: nothing further from reality.

Here's a simple destabiliser: we'll apply a linear filter to the spectrum of a certain soundtrack extract (equalization) and feed both the original piece and the processed one to the MLP. As emotion in audio doesn't appear to depend on equalization techniques (one song would be sad independently of an applied EQ), we will see if the neural network is also consistent in this way. This approach was proposed by Dr. Bob Sturm in his paper [29], encouraging MIR experts working in AER to be more skeptic and inquisitive in this field.

For this final (and even a little rushed) task, we've chosen two random extracts from the soundtrack database (the 327th and the 281st tracks in the 'set1' folder (see A.1)) and applied to them a different filter to their spectrum to see if this actually perturbs the neural network's judgement (MLP). Ten iterations for all files (10 predictions) have been run for this task, and the analysed extract wasn't part of the learning set in every case, as it would be a form of cheating from our part. The main results for both the original and the filtered piece for arousal and valence together are displayed in table 3.10.

As we can see, the predicted values for arousal and valence hardly move once the filter is applied. In fact, in accordance with the results in tables 3.5 and 3.6, the deviations for the arousal dimension are mightier than the ones for valence, as the former has been found to output less testing error. This is pretty interesting, as it could actually serve us as a confirmation that the neural network is actually classifying emotions and not some random independent phenomena or sound quality. Except, of course, we can't say this is true, as only two extracts have been used and there's no possible confidence in the results. It's expected from the author to expand the scope

Table 3.10: Results for the experiment involving processed (filtered) versions of a file to feed the MLP. The magnitudes displayed range from 0 to 100 for both arousal and valence.

Type	281	281 Filtered	327	327 Filtered	281 Diff	327 Diff
Arousal	47.54	51.06	69.25	70.75	3.52%	1.50%
Valence	46.29	53.45	31.92	37.17	7.16%	5.25%

of the project in this sense in the future, as one would have to look closer to see if the MLP doesn't really mind the application of a filter.

Finally, it's worth reflecting on the very assumption that filters don't affect emotional judgements at all. One could argue that, while the effect of these is not generally notable, it certainly is not negligible. For instance, sad pieces of music usually have a rich low-mid spectral range while happy ones tend to have a higher spectral centroid; and if one strips them from the audio file it could certainly be a source of confusion for both artificial and natural neural networks.

However, what Dr. Sturm is really suggesting in his article is that if a machine learning algorithm is found to be placing too much weight on a variable that if changed significantly the song would sound pretty much the same from an emotional point of view, then the algorithm is simply not looking in the right place and its predictions would be useless outside the idiosyncrasy of the used learning dataset.

Chapter 4

Conclusions

A lot of things have been discussed across the sections that hold this dissertation together, and most of them were completely unknown to the author himself at the time of starting the project, so a great load of new and exciting knowledge has been gained in these three and a half months of work.

In chapter 1 we've introduced the concepts of MIR and AER, providing the reader with both the conceptual and historical context before moving on to the next sections, way more mentally challenging.

Moving on to chapter 2, the four main parts of an MIR/AER process are outlined and then described in depth. *Feature Engineering* consisted on the coding and extraction of Low Level Descriptors (LLD) and audio features; *Feature Selection* was about the selection of the most relevant audio features; in *Model Engineering* we coded the machine learning maps of audio features to emotions (in our case, Artificial Neural Networks); and finally, *Model Selection* dealt with the selection of the optimal hyper-parameters of each Neural Network in order to achieve the best performance possible.

In chapter 3 we've presented some results for feature selection and model selection, along with the final model performances. These have been discussed rather inquisitively throughout the chapter and some weaknesses in some particular tasks have been spotted. It has also been proven by different methods that both neural network models actually do their job a priori, and the author has learned how delicate is the 'experiment's setup' phase for the neural networks' successful performance and optimal predictions.

These three core chapters provide the reader with context, theory and experiments in the field respectively, offering the possibility of learning about the field and the state of the art and even learning about the fundamentals of the processes which characterise

it, as this second chapter has been written with both didactic and expository intentions. With respect to the type of features and model themselves, Artificial Neural Networks appear to work fine for Low Level Descriptors, although some papers reference the use of High Level Descriptors like timbre or chord progression in AER investigations; which, depending on the type of analysed music, could be more relevant than LLD.

One of the issues that the field of AER is struggling with is the fact that researchers often get successful practices from Automatic Genre Recognition (AGR) and other sub-disciplines in MIR and apply them to an emotion recognition task without evaluating their a priori potential in this new context. Although successful at times, this approach seems to be rather problematic as genre, for instance, is a concept that holds very different properties from the ones emotion does. The parts of the human brain that regulate emotion (especially arousal) happen to be the most primitive ones, while genre perception often varies between cultures and individuals. This is also relevant to assess which and how many independent variables can compromise the relevance of the experiments in both sub-fields.

As Dr. Bob Sturm usually writes in his articles, a more inquisitive and skeptic kind of approach has to lead the research in MIR. The field needs of these attitudes to thrive. Being mindful of using specific feature sets and algorithms to work symbiotically given a certain context would allow the researcher to get full control of the task, and great achievements would naturally follow.

Appendix A

Further Logic

A.1 Digital Archive Tour

The project submission's folder holds this very PDF file with the dissertation along with two main folders: '*Codes*', which holds all the Matlab functions and scripts for the core MIR and AER tasks and '*Databases*', which contains all three used databases for AER and some Matlab code used for extracting and arranging the data.

The **Codes** folder contains the following sub-folders and files:

- **Acoustic Feature Extraction Set:** This folder stores the files used for both the feature engineering and the feature selection phases of the project.
 - Data: This folder contains the extracted features from the audio files in the databases 1 and 2 (by the names '*Features1*' and '*Features2*'), the LLD matrix from the audio files in database 3 ('*LLD3*') and the annotations for arousal, valence and emotions (both) for the database 1, calmness for database 2 (classification) and arousal and valence for database 3 ('*Arousal_Mean_1*', '*Valence_Mean_1*', '*Emotions_Mean_1*', '*Calmness_Mean_2*', '*Arousal_Mean_3*' and '*Valence_Mean_3*').
 - LLD and Basics: This folder contains the Low Level Descriptors' coded functions along with some basic required DSP functions that they need to operate properly. All of them are introduced by the descriptions of the function itself, its inputs and its outputs, and are explained through the present dissertation in 2.2.1. Here we list them all (the suffix '*afes*' stands for 'Acoustic Feature Extraction Set', the name of root folder storing these algorithms):

* Basics:

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'*afesBin2Freq*': Converts Bin indices to frequencies in Hz.

'*afesDelta*': Calculates the delta (derivative) of a vector.

'*afesDFT*': Calculates the Discrete Fourier Transform of a signal.

'*afesDFTFreq*': Calculates the Discrete Fourier Transform of a signal and outputs its frequency vector.

'*afesDFTppse*': Calculates the Discrete Fourier Transform of a signal and outputs its Periodogram-based Power Spectral Estimate.

'*afesDFTppseFreq*': Calculates the Discrete Fourier Transform of a signal and outputs both its Periodogram-based Power Spectral Estimate and its frequency vector.

'*afesDownSample*': Downsamples a certain signal by an integer dividing factor.

'*afesExtremes*': Calculates the extremes (minima or maxima) of a given vector.

'*afesExtremesVar*': Calculates the extremes (minima or maxima) of a given vector and, if no extreme is retrieved, the threshold parameter is changed accordingly until finding one.

'*afesFFT*': Calculates the Fast Fourier Transform of a given signal. It's twice faster than the DFT algorithm.

'*afesFreq2Bark*': Converts frequency in Hz to frequency in Barks.

'*afesFreq2Bin*': Converts frequency in Hz to Bin indices.

'*afesLoudnessSpectrum*': Calculates the Loudness Spectrum of a certain magnitude spectrum.

'*afesMonoConverter*': Converts a stereo file to a mono file.

'*afesSpectralPeaks*': Outputs the peaks of a given spectrum.

'*afesWindow*': Applies an analysis window to a signal.

* Low Level Descriptors (LLD):

'*afesEnergy*': Calculates the total energy of a given spectrum

'*afesEntropy*': Calculates the entropy of a given spectrum.

'*afesF0*': Calculates the Fundamental Frequency of a given signal.

'*afesFlux*': Calculates the spectral flux between two consecutive frames.

'*afesHNR*': Calculates the Harmonic to Noise Ratio of a given signal.

'*afesInharmonicity*': Calculates the inharmonicity of a given spectrum.

'*afesJitter*': Calculates the Jitter of a signal.

'*afesMFCC*': Retrieves the Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients of a certain spectrum.

'*afesRollOff*': Calculates the Roll-Off frequency for a certain spectrum.

'*afesSharpness*': Calculates the psychoacoustical sharpness of a given spectrum.

'*afesShimmer*': Calculates the Shimmer of a signal.

'*afesSpectralCentroid*': Calculates the centroid frequency of a given spectrum.

'*afesSpectralEnergy*': Calculates the energy in a given range of a given spectrum.

'*afesSpectralKurtosis*': Calculates the kurtosis of a certain spectrum.

'*afesSpectralSkewness*': Calculates the skewness of a given spectrum.

'*afesSpectralSlope*': Calculates the slope of a given spectrum.

'*afesSpectralVariance*': Calculates the variance of a certain spectrum.

'*afesZCR*': Calculates the Zero Crossing Rate of a give signal.

- 'Sample Files': This folder contains some sound files from the first database (extract from a soundtrack) that are used in the demo '*MIR_Example*' in the *Machine Learning* folder, also used to perform the experiments in 3.4. The 'Filtered' tag means that the audio has been processed by a high-pass filtered type of parametric EQ.
- 'Statistics': This folder contains the Statistical Functionals (SF) along with some basic required DSP functions that they need to operate properly, though these last ones have been all referenced in the 'Basics' section above. All of them are introduced by the descriptions of the function itself, its inputs and its outputs, and are explained through the present dissertation in 2.2.2.

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Here we list them all:

'*afesCentroid*': Calculates the centroid of a given vector.

'*afesFlatness*': Calculates the flatness of a given vector.

'*afesKurtosis*': Calculates the kurtosis of a given vector.

'*afesLinearRegression*': Applies a linear regression to a given vector.

'*afesLP*': Calculates the Linear Prediction Coefficients of a given vector.

'*afesPercentile*': Outputs different percentiles in a given vector.

'*afesQuadraticRegression*': Applies a quadratic regression to a given vector.

'*afesQuartile*': Outputs different quartiles and inter-quartile ranges in a given vector.

'*afesRDder*': Calculates the relative duration of a vector's rise and fall, along with positive and negative curvature, by differentiation processes.

'*afesRDslope*': Calculates the relative duration of a vector's rise and fall by calculating its instant dynamics.

'*afesSkewness*': Calculates the skewness of a given vector.

'*afesStandardDeviation*': Calculates the standard deviation of a given vector's magnitudes.

'*afesVariance*': Calculates the variance of a given vector.

- '*afesExtractor*': Retrieval function that retrieves all the features of a certain audio file or set of audio files. It works by dividing each audio file in frames, extracting all the LLD and their deltas from each frame and applying the statistical descriptors to all the LLD vectors. It's described in more detail in 2.2
- '*afesFeatureSelection*': Selects the most relevant features of a feature matrix as described in 2.3.
- 'Audio_Loader': Script that loads the audio files from one of the three databases and stores them in a cell, ready for feature extraction.
- 'Features_Index': Matlab data file storing the names of the 3081 features in order to retrieve the features' names when doing feature selection.

- **Machine Learning:** This folder stores the files used for both the model engineering and the model selection phases of the project.
 - Model Selection: This folder contains the results of the model selection phase of the project, storing the optimal values for the relevant hyper-parameters in each experiment setup. In this fashion, we have the optimal results for arousal, valence, both emotions and calmness for the MLP (*'Opt_MLP_Arousal'*, *'Opt_MLP_Valence'*, *'Opt_MLP_Emotions'*, *'Opt_MLP_Calmness'*), as well as the optimal values for both arousal and valence (model selection done with the arousal dimension) for the RNN-LSTM (*'Opt_RNN_LSTM'*).
 - Neural Networks: This folder stores the neural networks' functions, for both the MLP and the RNN-LSTM, along with the functions responsible for applying the activation function and the cost/metric function (*'mlActivation'* and *'mlCost'* respectively). The *'ml'* prefix stands for 'Machine Learning', the name of the root folder storing these algorithms. In this way, we also have their training functions (*'mlTrain_MLP'* and *'mlTrain_RNN_LSTM'*), their predicting functions (*'mlPredict_MLP'* and *'mlPredict_RNN_LSTM'*) and their actual whole implementation (*'mlNN_MLP_Classification'*, *'mlNN_MLP_Regression'* and *'mlNN_RNN_LSTM_Regression'*).
 - Results: This folder contains the final results of the experiments right after the model selection phase of the project, working with the retrieved optimal values for the hyper-parameters in each experiment setup. In this fashion, we have the final results for arousal, valence, both emotions and calmness for the MLP (*'Result_MLP_Arousal'*, *'Result_MLP_Valence'*, *'Result_MLP_Emotions'*, *'Result_MLP_Calmness'*), as well as the ones for arousal and valence for the RNN-LSTM (*'Results_RNN_LSTM_Arousal'*, *'Results_RNN_LSTM_Valence'*). For the regression results for MLP, though, a more sophisticated model performance approach has been carried out parallelly, as different metrics have been used, providing information about them all in the final 3-dimensional matrix. There are 6 different metrics applied to the results of the top 3 model selection ranking experiments and, as k fold cross-validation gives a mean value and a standard deviation one for all the k runs, the mean and the standard deviation of this mean and standard deviation have been also captured as an extra dimension, expressing the results in a final $[4 \times 6 \times 3]$ matrix.
 - *MIR_Example:* This file serves as a step by step guide for an MIR/AER process as described in the present dissertation in chapter 2 and the

experiment done in 3.4. It will use the files located in the '*Sample Files*' folder (located in the '*Acoustic Feature Extraction Set*' folder) as the cases of study and will ultimately predict their emotional dimensions (arousal and valence).

- *mlGradientChecking_MLP*: This script takes a certain input and output vector and performs gradient checking for the MLP's backpropagation algorithm as described in 3.1.
- *mlOptRetrieval*: This script allows the user to get a particular optimal hyper-parameter from the results of model selection. The process is very simple, as it runs through the results vectors (of length 2000 for MLP and 15 for RNN-LSTM), identifies the lowest error and retrieves the hyper-parameters associated with that particular result.
- *mlScaling*: This function applies different scaling functions to input and output data as described in the present dissertation in section 2.4. The inputs are usually standardised and the outputs normalised from 0 to 1.
- *mlScripts* (3 scripts): These pieces of code contain different initialization routines for the MLP's and the RNN-LSTM's typical tasks. The codes are divided into two different sections: *Model Selection* and *Model Performance*, as described in 3.3. This last one also allows a certain user to introduce custom parameters and run the neural network at hand. The scripts with these characteristics are '*mlScript_Classification_MLP*', '*mlScript_Regression_MLP*' and '*mlScript_Regression_RNN_LSTM*'.

The **Databases** folder, on the other hand, contains the following sub-folders and files:

- 1_Soundtracks: This is the first database, as described in 2.1.1. It's composed by two sets of audio files: *set1*, with 360 extracts and *set2* with 110. Each of these two folders includes a sub-folder with the audio files, their mean ratings (static) for both arousal and valence and the information related to each of one (the '*stimulus*' files). The database also includes a short manual in '.pdf' describing the database itself.
- 2_Emotify: This is the second database, as described in 2.1.2. It's composed by four sets of audio files from different musical genres with 100 samples each one. Ratings of all participants for classification are given in the '.csv' file, which the author of the present project arranged so to capture the mean of the ratings and

export them into a Matlab file ('*2_Emotify_All*'). IMPORTANT: all '.csv' files were extracted with the 'csvimport.m' function, coded by Ashish Sadanandan.

- 3_Emotion_In_Music: This is the third and last database, as described in 2.1.3. It's composed by one big set of audio files from different musical genres with 1000 samples in total, though only 744 were annotated properly. Ratings of all participants for classification are given in '.csv' files, which the author of this project arranged so to export them into Matlab files. The database also includes a short manual in '.pdf' describing the database itself and a parallel feature extraction process that the authors performed on it. IMPORTANT: all '.csv' files were extracted with the 'csvimport.m' function, coded by Ashish Sadanandan.

A.2 Pseudocode (Feature Engineering)

In this appendix section, the author provides the *pseudocode* of some of the algorithms featured in this dissertation in order to break down the logic behind their computation. The targeted algorithms for this purpose are both those that cannot be coded by just applying the correspondent main formula and those whose main code is complex, i.e. the ones composed by two or more sections involving distinct DSP processing techniques.

The output variables of the main function are displayed in brackets [] right next to the declaration of the function command; the input variables, on the other hand, are given in parenthesis () after the output ones.

The sections that characterize these algorithms are the following:

- **Basic Functions**: Building blocks of the rest of the functions *Algorithms 1 - 2*.
- **Low Level Descriptors (LLD)**: Building blocks of the rest of the functions *Algorithms 3 - 11*.
- **Statistical Functionals**: Building blocks of the rest of the functions *Algorithms 12 - 17*.

Finally, a glossary of the main variables featured in the coding is listed below.

- **x** : Mono signal.
- **Fs** : Sample Rate of a signal.
- **N** : Length of a signal.

- **Xmag**: Magnitude vector from the Fourier transform of the signal.

Algorithm 1 Delta (*afesDelta.m*)

```

1: function [Delta](v, win, type)
2:   if type = 'normal' then
3:     Calculate Derivative of v from win+1 to (End-win);
4:   end if
5:   if type = 'simplifiediffs' then
6:     Calculate Derivative of v by Simple Differences Method (Range = 2*win)
       from win+1 to (End-win);
7:   end if
8:   Calculate Derivative of v by Simple Differences Method (Range = 2) from 1 to
       win;
9:   Calculate Derivative of v by Simple Differences Method (Range = 2) from
       (End-win+1) to End;
10: end function

```

Algorithm 2 Extremes (with Threshold Variation) (*afesExtremesVar.m*)

```

1: function [pAmpl, pLocs](v, type, Th, C)
2:   if type = 'min' then
3:     Find Locations of Minima (Samples) in v;
4:   end if
5:   if type = 'max' then
6:     Find Locations of Maxima (Samples) in v;
7:   end if
8:   Apply Parabolic Interpolation (Samples) to Locations and Amplitudes of
       Extremes (Minima or Maxima);
9:   Apply Threshold to Amplitudes of Extremes;
10:  while NoExtremesbeloworabovetheThreshold do
11:    Add/Subtract C*Th to/from Th (Threshold);
12:  end while
13: end function

```

Algorithm 3 Loudness (*afesLoudness.m*)

```

1: function [Loud](Xmag, Filter)
2:   Convert Xmag (in amplitude) to Xdb (in decibels);
3:   if Filter = 'A' then
4:     Build "A weighting" filter;
5:   end if
6:   if Filter = 'B' then
7:     Build "B weighting" filter;
8:   end if
9:   if Filter = 'C' then
10:    Build "C weighting" filter;
11:  end if
12:  Apply built filter to Xmag;
13:  Convert Xdb (in decibels) to Xmag (in amplitude);
14:  Calculate Energy of Xmag;
15:  Calculate Loud with Energy and Constant;
16: end function

```

Algorithm 4 Zero Crossing Rate (*afesZCR.m*)

```

1: function [zcr](x)
2:   Set Counter to 0;
3:   for  $n = 2 : N$  do
4:     if  $\text{sign}(x(n)) \neq \text{sign}(x(n-1))$  AND  $x(n-1) \neq 0$  then
5:       Add 1 to Counter;
6:     end if
7:   end for
8:   Calculate zcr with Counter and N;
9: end function

```

Algorithm 5 Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (*afesMFCC.m*)

```

1: function [mfcc](P, Fs, N, Nf, Nc, fmin, fmax)
2:   Convert fmin and fmax (Hz) to fminm and fmaxm (Mels);
3:   Interpolate fminm and fmaxm with Nf points in between  $\rightarrow$  fm (vector in Mels);
4:   Convert fm (vector in Mels) to fh (vector in Hz);
5:   Convert fh (vector in Hz) to fb (vector in Bins);
6:   for  $n = 2 : \text{length}(x)$  do
7:     Build Filterbank;
8:   end for
9:   Calculate Logarithm of Filterbank  $\rightarrow$  LogFilt;
10:  Calculate Discrete Cosine Transform of LogFilt  $\rightarrow$  mfcc;
11:  Truncate mfcc to Nc terms;
12: end function

```

Algorithm 6 Spectral Energy (*afesSpectralEnergy.m*)

```

1: function [SE](Xmag, Fs, N, fmin, fmax)
2:   Convert fmin and fmax (Hz) to fminb and fmaxb (Bins);
3:   for n = fminb : fmaxb do
4:     Calculate Sum of Energies of Xmag(n) → SE;
5:   end for
6: end function

```

Algorithm 7 Spectral Roll Off Frequency (*afesRollOff.m*)

```

1: function [ROF](Xmag, Fs, N, ROP)
2:   Convert Frequency bin vector (Bins) to Frequency vector (Hz);
3:   Calculate Energy of Xmag;
4:   Calculate Roll Off Energy with Energy and ROP;
5:   Set Parameter to length(Xmag);
6:   Set Index to length(Xmag);
7:   Set Direction to -1;
8:   while Parameter > 1 do
9:     Set Parameter to Parameter/2;
10:    Set Index to Index + Direction*Parameter;
11:    Calculate Energy High Frequencies of Xmag(index:end);
12:    Calculate Energy Low Frequencies of Xmag(1:index);
13:    if Energy – EnergyLowFrequencies >= 0 then
14:      Set Direction to 1;
15:    else
16:      Set Direction to -1;
17:    end if
18:  end while
19: end function

```

Algorithm 8 Spectral Entropy (*afesEntropy.m*)

```

1: function [Entropy](Xmag)
2:   Calculate Power of Xmag;
3:   Calculate Power Sum of Power;
4:   Calculate Ppmf with Power and Power Sum;
5:   Calculate Entropy with Ppmf;
6: end function

```

Algorithm 9 Psychoacoustical Sharpness (*afesSharpness.m*)

```

1: function [Sharpness](Xmag, Fs, N, NB)
2:   Calculate Loudness Spectrum and Frequency Vector of Xmag;
3:   Convert Frequency vector (Hz) to Bark vector (Barks);
4:   for  $i = 1 : NumBarks * 10$  do
5:     Find Loudness of 0.1 Bark long bands from Loudness Spectrum →
     LoudBark(i);
6:     if LoudBark(i) = NaN then
7:       Set LoudBark(i) to 0;
8:     end if
9:   end for
10:  Build z vector;
11:  Build g(z) function;
12:  Calculate Sharpness with LoudBark, g(z) and z;
13: end function

```

Algorithm 10 Fundamental Frequency (*afesF0.m*)

```

1: function [f0, Minima](x, Fs, Th, L, w, Extr)
2:   Calculate Difference Equation of x;
3:   Calculate Cumulative Normalized Mean Difference of Difference Equation;
4:   Find Minima of Cumulative Normalized Mean Difference → Minima;
5:   Find Fundamental Period (Samples-1) in Minima;
6:   Convert Fundamental Period to Fundamental Frequency (Hz) → f0;
7:   Convert Minima (Samples-1) to Minima (Hz) → Minima;
8: end function

```

Algorithm 11 Harmonic to Noise Ratio (HNR) (*afesHNR.m*)

```

1: function [HNR](x, Fs, f0)
2:   Calculate t0 (Period) with Fs and f0;
3:   Calculate Autocorrelation Parameter of x → r1;
4:   Calculate Autocorrelation Parameter of x from t0+1 to End → r2;
5:   Normalize r1;
6:   Normalize r2;
7:   Calculate HNR with r1 and r2;
8: end function

```

Algorithm 12 Quartile and Interquartile Ranges (*afesQuartile.m*)

```

1: function [Q, IQR](v)
2:   Sort v in Ascending order → vs;
3:   Calculate Median of values of vs below the median of vs → Q(1);
4:   Calculate Median of vs → Q(2);
5:   Calculate Median of values of vs above the median of vs → Q(3);
6:   Subtract First term of vs from Q(1) → IQR(1);
7:   Subtract Q(1) from Q(3) → IQR(2);
8:   Subtract Q(3) from Last term of vs → IQR(3);
9: end function

```

Algorithm 13 Percentile (*afesPercentile.m*)

```

1: function [P](v, percent)
2:   Calculate Percentile index from Length of v;
3:   Calculate Percentile magnitude from vs  $\rightarrow$  P;
4: end function

```

Algorithm 14 Relative Duration (Magnitude and Slope) (*afesRDmag.m*, *afesRDslope.m*)

```

1: function [RD](v, dir)
2:   if dir = 1 then
3:     Calculate Terms of v when v is rising  $\rightarrow$  N;
4:   end if
5:   if dir = -1 then
6:     Calculate Terms of v when v is falling  $\rightarrow$  N;
7:   end if
8:   Calculate RD from Number of Terms and Length of v;
9: end function

```

Algorithm 15 Relative Duration (Derivates) (*afesRDder.m*)

```

1: function [RD](v, dir, type)
2:   if type = 1 then
3:     Calculate First Derivative of v  $\rightarrow$  vd;
4:   end if
5:   if type = 2 then
6:     Calculate Second Derivative of v  $\rightarrow$  vd;
7:   end if
8:   if dir = 1 then
9:     Calculate Terms of vd Greater than 0  $\rightarrow$  N;
10:  end if
11:  if dir = -1 then
12:    Calculate Terms of vd Less than 0  $\rightarrow$  N;
13:  end if
14:  Calculate RD from Number of Terms and Length of v;
15: end function

```

Algorithm 16 Linear Prediction Coefficients (*afesLP.m*)

```

1: function [LPC](v, N)
2:   Calculate Autocorrelation Vector of Lag 1 to N of v;
3:   Build Autocorrelation Squared Matrix from Autocorrelation Vector;
4:   Calculate LPC from Autocorrelation Squared Matrix and Autocorrelation
   Vector;
5: end function

```

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